

METHODOLOGY FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF MOTION COORDINATION IN STUDENTS WITH VISUAL IMPAIRMENTS

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Abstract. This article describes selected methods and techniques for developing coordination skills through physical exercises in children with visual impairments.

Key words: modern dynamics, development, perform, special training.

МЕТОДИКА РАЗВИТИЯ КООРДИНАЦИИ ДВИЖЕНИЙ У СТУДЕНТОВ С НАРУШЕНИЕМ ЗРЕНИЯ

Аннотация. В данной статье описаны избранные методы и приемы развития координационных способностей посредством физических упражнений у детей с нарушением зрения.

Ключевые слова: современная динамика, развитие, выступление, специальная подготовка.

Relevance. The young generation, which is growing in the conditions of the current rapidly changing time, is setting tasks for adaptation to social and political processes, as well as to the environment. The modern dynamics of the development of society is such that the requirements for training a specialist are becoming more important than ever. One of the reasons for this phenomenon is determined by the changing of society, the imposition of new requirements for living conditions and the issue of rapid adaptation to these changes.

Impaired activity of visual analyzers due to the presence of eye defects in children leads to a decrease in movement activity, and also causes great difficulty when students perform various actions.

Visual analyzers occupy a key place in the development of children's movement activity.

The actions of children with eye defects depend on the development of management qualities that provide exactly the same and accurate, timely, rational and presentable solution.

Lack of movement in students with visual impairment leads to the appearance of excess mass in the body, impaired posture, deterioration of vision, as well as a decrease in the functionality of the cardiovascular and respiratory systems of the body. Cases ($R > 0.05$) are observed when children with changes in vision are confidently lagging behind their peers in many indicators.

Object of study: the process of training carried out with students with visual impairment of Uzdjtsu.

The subject of the study: tools and techniques aimed at developing the ability to coordinate movement in students with visual impairments.

When special training is carried out after the detection of the disease in a person, it is possible to correct the existing shortcomings and prevent the formation of incorrect movement, thereby

allowing the development of a full-fledged person who actively participates in social life, takes a worthy place in socially useful work.

A number of studies have been carried out to improve children's eye defects, to improve their ability to overlap movements, and the insufficient number of programs aimed at developing Movement Coordination in this nosology has been found as a result of the evacuation of scientific literature.

In adaptive physical education, when performing movement correction activities, the visual system requires the use of an individual stratified approach, taking into account ophthalmological indicators, secondary deviations, physical loads and a description of certain types of restrictions of physical exercises.

The purpose of the study. Development of motion coordination by normalizing the selected means and methods, taking into account the indicators of vision.

This is done through the following tasks:

study of the dependence of the development of the ability to coordinate movement on age characteristics in students with eye defects;

justification of the effectiveness of methods and Means for the correction and development of coordination movements in students with violations in visual activity in additional classes of adaptive physical education.

Special methodology of research.

The methodology of the study selected various cases of static mode to determine the ability to coordinate movement in children with weak vision and blind eyes. At the expense of the introduction of exercises, the results of the initial study were determined, then it is required to carry out some kind of variable movement activity in order to develop the coordination ability of this movement, and the exercises in the re-static mode are evaluated. This study is recommended for practice as an adjuvant exercise in enhancing any ability to work Goal-Oriented after various variable movement activities in children with a weak seer, impaired eye ability.

To determine the degree of development of the Coordination of movement of students, test tests are carried out in the lessons of improving sports pedagogical skills using the following exercises:

With the left foot resting on the left hand above, the right foot on the side 30° in the position of right hand holding the position on the side (30 seconds)

Standing on the left foot, the left hand is ahead, with the right hand holding the right foot in a bent position behind the balance to maintain (30 seconds)

Standing on the right leg torso 90o in a bent position arms extended forward, right leg back 90o to maintain balance with the raised;

Standing on the right leg torso 90o in a bent position arms extended to the side, right leg back 90o to maintain balance with the raised;

The second meter starts on the” start ” command and continues until the time allotted for the exercise is over.

To develop the Coordination of movement of students with visual impairments, the following special developmental exercise program has been developed by us.

T/r	Program sections *	Duration of exercise	Meyori	Rest time	Days of the week
1	Standing in one line	53,7-55,5 sec.	3	1 min.	Monday
2	Standing on one leg	7,25 sec	5-6	1-1,5 min.	
3	Walking in place with eyes closed	30 sec	3	30 sek.	
4	Walking along a line	12,5-15,2 sec	3	1-1,5 min.	Wednesday
5	"Swallow(s)"	3,5 above seconds	3	1- min	
6	Maintaining balance on one leg on a solitary stick	3,5 above seconds	3	1- min	
7	Balance storage on one leg on special pads	5 above seconds	3	1- min	Friday
8	Balance storage in a semi-peak position on special pads	30 above seconds	3	1- min	
9	Jump into the swallow position at a speed that exceeds the forward spine	30 above seconds	3	1- min	
10	Maintaining balance on one leg after a flipping exercise	30 sek.dan yuqori vaqt oralig'ida	3	1- min	

Note: when performing each exercise, the guide should tell the children their mistakes and shortcomings, and try to eliminate them on the spot as much as possible.

The program developed by us to develop the Coordination of movement of students with visual impairments was carried out 3 times a week in the lessons of improving sports pedagogical skills.

Average value of motion coordination in students with visual impairment before and after the study

Table 1

Content of exercises	Status	Execution time is the arithmetic mean value ($\bar{X}$)	
		Before the study	After the study
With the left foot resting on the left hand above, the right foot on the side 30° in the position of right hand holding the position on the side within 30 seconds	Static RECM in a calm state	22	27
	Static RECM after any dynamic topshi	18	23
With the left foot resting on the left hand the left hand is ahead, with the right hand the right foot in the back bent position while holding the mouthpiece to maintain Within 30 seconds	Static RECM in a calm state	21	27
	Static RECM after any dynamic topshi	17	24
Standing on the right leg torso 90o in a bent position arms extended forward, right leg back 90o to maintain balance with the raised	Static RECM in a calm state	23	28
	Static RECM after any dynamic topshi	18	24
Standing on the right leg torso 90o in a bent position arms extended to the side, right leg back 90o to maintain balance with the raised	Static RECM in a calm state	24	28
	Static RECM after any dynamic topshi	19	25

The results of the study show that under the influence of methods and means, the rationing of physical loads and their intensity, the demonstrative dynamics of the experimental group were positively influenced, which shows the effectiveness of pedagogic scientific experience.

Children with visual impairment have an increased level of development of motion coordination, increasing their chances of movement. In order to correct and develop the qualities of movement in relation to students who lagged behind in performing actions, additional classes of adaptive physical education were used.

The results before the study show that in our control exercise 1, the duration of the exercise performed in the static plan was 22 seconds, while the after-study indicator changed by 27 seconds, while after performing dynamic work, we can see that this figure was 18 seconds, while after the study it was better than 23 seconds.

control 2, it was 21 seconds in static mode, 17 seconds after performing dynamic work. After the study, its indicators changed to static 27 seconds, and after performing dynamic work-24 seconds.

In our control exercise 3, the static RECM was 23 seconds, after performing dynamic work it was 18 seconds. The indicators after the study changed to static 28 seconds, and dynamic 24 seconds after performing work.

In our control exercise 4, the static RECM was 24 seconds, after performing dynamic work it was 19 seconds. After the study, its indicators changed to static 28 seconds, and after performing dynamic work-25 seconds.

The test results, carried out to determine the degree of dynamics of the development of motion coordination, determined the statistically reliable changes ($R < 0.05$) in all age groups under study.

Conclusion. Ending the study conducted, it is necessary to note that students with various disorders in visual activity were found to be much lower in terms of various indicators of movement compared to their peers. It was found that the degree of development of motor coordination in children with eye defects has a similar description in the development of age dynamics.

As a result of the stylistic influence on the experimental group, it was found that the growth rates of the studied coordination indicators are high. It was found that the Test Test indicators carried out in students with visual depression correspond to the level of regulatory requirements for physical education “medium”, “above the middle”.

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